

END-TO-END DESIGN OF A ROBOTIC EXPLORATION SYSTEM FOR LUNAR LAVA TUBES.

I. Terlizzi^{1,a}, R. González-Cinca², S. Chiodioni^{1,3}, G. Colombatti^{1,3}, ¹CISAS G. Colombo, University of Padova, Italy ²Department of Physics, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech. c/ E. Terradas 5, 08860 Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain ³DII, University of Padova, Italy, ^airene.terlizzi@phd.unipd.it

Introduction: Lunar lava tubes are scientifically interesting and strategically relevant targets for future exploration missions with a view to possible settlement. These environments offer potential protection from radiation and micrometeorites, less extreme temperature variations than the surface, and preserve traces of the Moon's geological history. However, they pose significant engineering challenges due to difficulty of access, lack of natural lighting, limited communication links, and limited energy availability.

This work presents the end-to-end design of a robotic exploration system conceived to operate in such extreme lunar underground environments. The study includes the definition of the system-level architecture, the development of guidance, navigation and control (GNC), the thermal modelling of a representative lunar pit, the design of a power supply architecture and experimental validation through a functional breadboard prototype.

Luna Lava Tubes: Lunar lava tubes are subsurface cavities formed during basaltic volcanic activity, primarily associated with the mare regions of the Moon. These structures originate when the outer layer of a lava flow solidifies faster than the inner core leaving an empty conduct. Structural weakening or meteoroid impacts can cause partial roof collapse, generating skylights that provide natural access points to the subsurface. [1]

Orbital imagery have revealed multiple candidate skylights distributed across lunar mare basins. These features are characterized by near-vertical pit walls, overhanging rims, and shadowed interiors, strongly suggesting the presence of underlying cavities. The dimensions of inferred lava tubes are expected to exceed those typically observed on Earth due to the Moon's lower gravity, potentially resulting in large, stable subsurface voids extending over considerable distances.[2]

From a scientific perspective, lunar lava tubes are of high interest for several reasons like the preservation of geological records, volatile retention, thermal stability, radiation shielding, potential for future infrastructure [1]

The absence of direct solar illumination prevents conventional photovoltaic energy harvesting within the caves. Communication with surface assets may be obstructed. Access through skylights requires controlled vertical mobility and precise descent operations.

System architecture overview: The system architecture was defined using a mission-oriented systems engineering approach, starting from the envi-

ronmental constraints and operational requirements typical of lunar lava tubes. The platform was designed as a dual-segment system consisting of:

- Vertical mobility module: Responsible for descent through a skylight and controlled access inside the lava tube, and once inside the pit, acting as a relay between the system inside and the system on the surface.
- Legged mobility module: A hexapod platform that deploys once inside the cave to perform underground exploration and environmental surveys.

The system was designed to be compact (around 25 kg for the whole system and 6 kg for the legged module) while addressing the challenges of operating in this type of environment.

This modular configuration allows for the decoupling of mission phases: access operations are separated from mobility within the cave and scientific activities.

Figure 1: CAD model of the two subsystem coupled (A. Vertical mobility module, B. Legged mobility module)

Guidance, Navigation and Control: A complete GNC system was developed and implemented in MATLAB/Simulink to ensure stable and robust operation during descent phases.

The control architecture employs: PID-based trajectory tracking for position control, quaternion-based attitude control, and instantaneous rotation axis.

The controller was tested in the presence of modelled disturbances to evaluate its robustness, stability, and convergence behaviour. Disturbances were introduced in order to evaluate the system's ability to maintain performance.

Power supply architecture: The power supply architecture is designed to ensure continuous operation even in the absence of direct sunlight. It combines thermal energy storage and laser wireless power transfer (LWPT).

During the lunar day, the exposed platforms collect solar energy through photovoltaic panels to power the on-board systems and recharge the batteries sized for peak loads.

For night-time operation, a surface-based Thermal Wadi system stores solar energy as sensible heat within the thermally enhanced regolith. The stored heat can be converted to electricity via a Brayton cycle or used directly for thermal regulation, ensuring both power generation and survival heating during prolonged darkness. [3]

Hexapods operating inside lava tubes require alternative methods of energy supply.

Underground energy transfer is carried out via LWPT: Electrical energy powers laser diodes that transmit to a photovoltaic receiver with peak efficiency on the same wavelength as the laser. Despite relatively efficient components, cascading conversion losses limit end-to-end performance to approximately 10-14%. [4]

Figure 2: Sketch of the LWPT (A. and B. as before, C. is the rover responsible for taking the system to the pit, not part of this study)

Experimental Breadboard: To validate the integration of the subsystem, a functional prototype was built on a breadboard.

The breadboard integrates: Environmental sensors (temperature and humidity), a Geiger-Müller tube for radiation measurement, and a moisture sensor for water research in the regolith.

In parallel, a hexapod leg prototype was designed and tested to validate the kinematic modelling and mechanical feasibility.

Although not representative of a flight model, the breadboard provided a proof-of-concept validation and supported the iterative study of the system design.

Conclusion: This work presents a comprehensive mission study integrating systems engineering, control design, energy management, and experimental validation for robotic exploration of lunar lava tubes.

The proposed architecture demonstrates the technical feasibility of a modular exploration system capable of descending into underground environments and operating under extreme thermal and energy conditions.

References:

[1] Sauro, F., Pozzobon, R., Massironi, M., De Berardinis, P., Santagata, T., & De Waele, J. (2020). Lava tubes on Earth, Moon and Mars: A review on their size and morphology revealed by comparative planetology. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 209, 103288..

[2] Haruyama, J., Hioki, K., Shirao, M., Morota, T., Hiesinger, H., Van Der Bogert, C. H., ... & Pieters, C. M. (2009). Possible lunar lava tube skylight observed by SELENE cameras. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 36(21)

[3] Fleith, P., Cowley, A., Pou, A. C., Lozano, A. V., Frank, R., Córdoba, P. L., & González-Cinca, R. (2020). In-situ approach for thermal energy storage and thermoelectricity generation on the Moon: Modelling and simulation. *Planetary and Space Science*, 181, 104789.

[4] Sun, L., Kang, J., Bai, Y., & Jin, P. (2025, January). Design and efficiency optimization of distributed laser wireless power transmission systems through centralized scheduling and current regulation. In *Photonics* (Vol. 12, No. 1, p. 30). MDPI.